

Nickel(II)-ion selective electrode and its application in the determination of stability constant of metal complexes

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A new Ni^{II}-ion selective electrode has been developed. Stability constant of Ni^{II}-complex of PAR has been determined using this electrode.

Morazzani-Pelletier and Baffier¹ were the first to develop an electrode responsive towards Ni^{II} ion. The first precipitate-based Ni^{II} ion selective electrode² was based on different precipitates of metal with organic chelating agents. Electrodes based on nickel sulfide as electroactive material give poor response towards Ni^{II} ion³. The nickel selenide and nickel telluride based electrodes show response in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} to 1×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ of Ni^{II} ion but the response curve is not linear in this range. A number of other workers have developed Ni^{II} ion selective electrode using different electroactive materials⁴.

Ni^{II} can be complexed with thiopentone [sodium 5-ethyl-(1-methylbutyl)-2-thiobarbiturate]. Using this compound as an electroactive material an attempt has been made to develop a new Ni^{II} ion selective electrode. The present paper describes the preparation of this electrode, study of the characteristics of the electrode and its application in the determination of metal-ligand stability constant.

Results and Discussion

Electrode response: The electrode was first conditioned in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of Ni^{II} ion till it attained a stable equilibrium and then used to determine the characteristics of the electrode. The electrode potentials for a series of standard solutions of Ni^{II} ion in the range 5.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ were measured. The slope was found to be 27 mV per decade change in Ni^{II} ion concentration.

Effect of pH: pH of the 0.01 mol dm⁻³ Ni^{II} solution was varied by adding NaOH or HCl. The potential remained unchanged in the pH range 2.0–7.0. This is the working range of pH for the electrode.

Response time: The electrode was first dipped in 0.01 mol dm⁻³ of Ni^{II} ion solution and suddenly the concentration of the solution was changed to 0.001 mol dm⁻³. It took 30 s to give a constant potential. Hence 30 s may be regarded as the response time of the electrode.

Interference by ions: The cationic interferences due to

other ions were studied by the determination of selectivity coefficients by mixed solution methods⁵. The electrode potentials were recorded in mixed solutions having a fixed concentration of interferent, B (1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) and varying concentrations (1×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³) of Ni^{II} solution. The selectivity coefficients calculated from the plot of potential of electrode system vs concentration of cations are: Mg^{II}, 0.038; Mn^{II}, 0.100; Zn^{II}, 0.004; Co^{II}, 0.060 and Al^{III}, 0.0004. Owing to the hydrolysis of Fe^{III}, the selectivity coefficient in presence of this ion could not be determined.

Applications: In the study of metal-ligand equilibrium the ion-selective electrodes find wide applications⁶ because free metal ion concentration or the free ligand concentration can be determined directly.

The perusal of literature⁷ shows that the reported values of stability constant of Ni^{II} complex formed with PAR are not consistent and therefore, it was decided to reinvestigate the system using Ni^{II} ion selective electrode as a probe.

Ni^{II} forms a 1 : 2 complex with PAR⁸,

charges are omitted for simplicity.

The overall stability constant (β_2) is given by

$$\beta_2 = \beta_2' \phi^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } \phi = 1 + \frac{[H]}{K_{d1}} + \frac{[H]^2}{K_{d1}K_{d2}} \quad (3)$$

K_{d1} and K_{d2} are the first and second dissociation constant of PAR and β_2' is the conditional stability constant whose value can be determined at particular pH and is given by

$$\beta_2' = \frac{[ML_2]}{(M^\circ - [ML_2])(L^\circ - [ML_2])^2} \quad (4)$$

where, M° and L° are total metal and ligand concentration, respectively. On rearranging eqn. (4), we get,

$$\frac{[M][L^{\circ}]^2}{(M^{\circ} - [M])} = \frac{1}{\beta_2} + 4[M]\{L^{\circ} - (M^{\circ} - [M])\} \quad (5)$$

From eqns. (2) and (5) one can get,

$$\frac{[M]L^{\circ}}{(M^{\circ} - [M])} \frac{1}{\phi^2} = \frac{1}{\beta_2 L^{\circ}} + \frac{4[M]\{L^{\circ} - (M^{\circ} - [M])\}}{\phi^2 L^{\circ}} \quad (6)$$

If total metal and ligand concentration are kept constant and pH of the solution is varied then a plot of

$$\frac{[M]L^{\circ}}{(M^{\circ} - [M])} \frac{1}{\phi^2} \text{ against } \frac{[M]\{L^{\circ} - (M^{\circ} - [M])\}}{\phi^2 L^{\circ}}$$

would give a straight-line with an intercept equal to $1/\beta_2 L^{\circ}$, thus enabling one to calculate the overall stability constant of the complex.

A series of solutions were prepared in which the concentration of Ni ion and PAR were kept constant (1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), but pH was varied in the range 5.05–5.45, keeping the ionic strength constant at 0.1 M. The electrode potential of each solution was measured and the corresponding values of Ni^{II} ion were obtained from the calibration curve. The dissociation constant being known⁷, the free ligand concentration and therefore the value of log β_2 was calculated to be 21.45. The value reported in the literature⁹ is 25.1. The difference in the values may be due to the fact that in the latter case spectrophotometric technique has been adopted and also the experimental conditions are different.

Experimental

Preparation of electroactive material : To a solution (100 ml) of NiCl₂.6H₂O (0.238 g; AnalaR), a solution (100 ml) containing thiopentone (0.528 g; Abbot Lab.) was added when a light yellowish green coloured complex was obtained. The solution was allowed to evaporate at room temperature (~30°) for a few days. The resulting solid was washed with double-distilled water and then dried. This precipitate was used as the electroactive material for the electrode.

Preparation of membrane : The dried electroactive material (150 mg) was mixed with Araldite (Ciba-Geigy, 600 mg) and the paste was spread over a Whatman filter paper (No. 42) to 0.1 mm thick layer and air-dried for 48 h.

Preparation of electrode : The above filter paper was separated from the membrane by dipping it in a solution of Ni^{II} ion. Any portion of the filter paper adhering to the sur-

face of the membrane was removed to obtain a disc. A small portion was cut from the disc and was fixed with Araldite to one end of a glass tube (1 cm dia × 15 cm) and it was dried for 24 h. The tube was filled with 0.1 mol dm⁻³ Ni^{II} ion solution and kept immersed in the Ni^{II} ion solution of same strength for 1 week. The saturated calomel electrode was used as internal as well as the external reference electrode.

The entire electrode system for the measurements can be represented as

Internal reference electrode (SCE)	Internal reference solution Ni ion 0.1 mol dm ⁻³	Ion-selective membrane	Sample solution	External reference electrode (SCE)
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A Philips PR 9405 pH/mV meter with a saturated calomel electrode was used. The pH was measured by Orion Ionalyzer-901. All measurements were made at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^{\circ}$).

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